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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 4

Pages: 358-369

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1967

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12576247

Manuscript Accepted: 05-20-2024

Application of Teacher-Made Task-Based Module in Task-Based Language Teaching Under New Normal

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Abstract

This study focused on the effectiveness of Teacher- Made Task-Based Approach Module which consists of pre-task, actual task, post task review, and assignment or practice uploaded in the Learning Management System in relation to students' academic achievement in English 10 under new normal in San Emmanuel National High School with a problem posed in terms of reading comprehension among students. To provide good analysis, an experimental research design was used. The study subjects were 40 G-10 students. Mean was utilized to determine the validity of the Task-based Approach Module and the academic achievement of the control group and experimental group. Results revealed that the Task-based Approach Module was highly valid in content, relevance, instructional quality, and acceptability, implying that it is suitable for use in Task-Based Language Teaching. Hence, the transmuted pretest scores of both groups did not meet the expectation with similar achievement of learning. The posttest scores revealed that the experimental group performed better than the control group. The EG obtained a satisfactory level. In contrast, the CG has obtained a fairly satisfactory level. The t-test revealed that the students increased their scores during the posttest compared to their pretest scores. Furthermore, the mean gain scores revealed that the EG performed better than the CG student. The application of the Task-Based Approach learning module was effective as to the content and relevance of task-based activities through the task cycle in the new normal, which contributed to the increase in performance scores of the respondents. It concluded that the Task-based Approach Module had effectively and significantly improved the students' academic achievement in English. Further, It was suggested that further research be conducted, with an emphasis on the learning styles of the students and an investigation into how well the Task-based Approach Module works to improve students' reading, writing, and listening skills in both public educational settings and other levels of education, such as upper secondary ones.

Keywords: *task-based approach module, Task-based language teaching, academic achievement*

Introduction

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) views the process of meaning-making as the primary focus of language instruction. It's about the outcome of tasks. Problem-solving, creative thinking, sharing personal experiences, talking about themselves, their families, interests, likes and dislikes, and needs in the correct socio-cultural environment are all examples of it. It provides language components for learners to do real-world tasks.

The Philippine educational system focused initially on the K–12 curriculum, which helps students gain lifelong skills. It adopted blended learning under the new normal, which allows for the expansion of various teaching and learning approaches. Briones (2020) notes that the department's answer to the issues during Covid-19 is the basic education learning continuity plan. One of the blended learning modes is the Learning Management System (LMS). A type of software that lets teachers create virtual courses, assign assignments, track score inputs, and administer online quizzes to measure comprehension (Llego, 2020).

Subsequently, there is a reading comprehension problem among students at San Emmanuel National High School (SENHS), as evidenced by the results of the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2018, which found that 80% of students in the Philippines, particularly in Region XII, did not reach a minimum level of reading proficiency, and by the outcomes of the National Achievement Test (NAT), which show a drop in English proficiency levels (Gonzales, 2019). In addition, English language instructors are not fully aware of TBLT or how to apply it effectively in their classrooms (Barrot, 2018). As Tarek (2016) underscores distance learning entails a high level of interaction. Teachers should be able to design language activities that cater to learners' needs, and behavior to become successful in language learning (Ulla, 2017). On the other hand, Ramamurthy (2019) found that utilizing a task-based approach throughout the intervention has favorably improved the grades earned in the post-test, however, most study outcomes in Asian nations suggest that TBLT implementation is difficult and may vary due to cultural differences (Isabel & Farfan, 2019). The linguistic ability of teachers may also influence student learning (Nemati et al., 2017). Furthermore, according to Permatasari (2021), genuine output is appreciated when it is in the form of an English language paper that combines real-life situations that students have faced. Therefore, from a critically informed standpoint, TBLT has only engaged with a portion of the factors. It could be advantageous to incorporate a more critical point of view into curriculum development, task design, and content (Crookes & Ziegler, 2021). With this situation, this study sought to offer a Task-Based Approach Module (TBA-Module) in language teaching incorporated in LMS to enhance learners' reading comprehension skills through immersing in TBLT. Thus, the study aimed to determine its effect on students' academic achievement in English 10 under the new normal.

Research Questions

The study identified the effectiveness of the TBA-Module utilizing the Learning Management System (LMS) in the new normal in

improving the student's academic achievement in English 10. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of validity of the Tasked-Based Approach Module in terms of content, relevance, instructional quality, and acceptability?
2. What is the level of students' academic achievement in the pretest and posttest?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control and experimental groups?
4. Is there a significant difference between the level of academic achievement of the control and experimental groups?
5. Is there a significant difference between the mean gain scores of the control group and experimental groups?

Literature Review

Ziegler (2016), in his paper Taking technology to task: technology-mediated TBLT, performance, and production, explains that situated learning and task-based learning ensure that resources acquired in the classroom are applied to the outside environment for practical purposes and practice because speaking is an interactive, transactional skill that is the result of collaboration with multiple participants. Whereas the fear of speaking has slowly vanished owing to task-based learning in the classroom, according to a TBLT research by Aqmar et al. (2020).

Furthermore, some instructors' participation with TBLT concepts has strengthened the emphasis on meaningful, real, interactive assignments that students find compelling and that help them gain fluency in the target language (East 2017). TBLT, on the other hand, has become frequently used in foreign language environments, notably in Asian nations, where the majority of the study's findings show that it is difficult to implement. Meanwhile, several publications concentrated on the difficulties that TBLT poses when applied in FL settings (Isabel & Farfan, 2019).

In addition, according to Van Loi (2020), learners may need to be acquainted with the task-based learning approach in order to be effective since they are too habituated to their traditional classroom teaching and learning methods. As a result of having a sense of control, the learner will be more driven to complete the procedure. While the students are active participants in the process, professors function as facilitators, observers, or counselors. Several research were undertaken to see how it affected language acquisition, taking into account the various aspects of task-based language instruction (Dergisi, 2018). Meanwhile, the ESL teaching environment could not ensure that all students could grasp the lesson in English (Hapsari, 2020).

The activity types are made up of three main activity kinds proposed by Prabhu (and mentioned by Jeon): information gap, reasoning gap, and opinion gap. Meanwhile, based on the learners' requirements, interests, and abilities on the NA, the subject matters to be taught or activity themes consist of three tiers of users: basic user, autonomous user, and competent user. Furthermore, in individual, pair, small-group, and whole-class modes, the settings of the activities in executing tasks are varied (Sundari et al., 2018).

Consequently, the Effect of Task-Based Instruction in Developing the English-Speaking Abilities of Ninth-Graders was shown to be beneficial in improving English-speaking skills in Cambodian schools, according to a research. TBI was shown to be a successful method for developing learners' English-speaking abilities. Despite the class size, it met their requirements and interests and provided an acceptable environment for language acquisition. These claims are similar of Long (2014) and Willis (1996). The TBI technique was incorporated into the English Grade 9 coursebook through a little and affordable modification that aided in improving academic performance. Having said all of that, TBI may offer a useful educational substitute for addressing typical issues that arise when teaching and developing English speaking abilities (Nget et al., 2020).

Ulla's (2017) study reveals that students doing different tasks in their language classroom were positive compared to those not exposed to it.

In contrast, despite the students' strong motivation to enhance their speaking abilities and the number of students who were highly motivated to use English in the classroom, a number of them still found it difficult to utilize English in speaking while conversing with their classmates (51 percent) and their instructor (42 percent). It was clear that many of them were just moderately motivated to use the English language (Ulla, 2017).

Notwithstanding these shifts in the background of second language education, task-based language teaching (TBLT) continues to be the most popular method in language classrooms (Barrot, 2016).

TBI uses both pedagogical and practical difficulties to provide students the chance to engage in worthwhile activity. In the former, students are required to communicate with one another. The latter include activities like listening, problem-solving, sharing personal experiences, and comparing, among others, that are based on real materials (Toro et al., 2018).

On one hand, the pre-task phase exposes learners to the topic at hand and encourages them to complete the major activities. The information-gap activity phase includes question and response and describing an image. Following that, the task cycle or "during task" phase allows students to complete needed activities related to fluency, accuracy, and complexity of utilizing the target language, which are monitored by the teachers. Finally, the post-task phase serves to repeat the exercise and provide feedback or thoughts (Sundari et al., 2018). The learners must negotiate the work with the assistance of the instructor, whose purpose is to provide learning chances in class.

Furthermore, according to the results of the OECD Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), which evaluates what students know in reading, mathematics, and science, as well as what they can do with what they know, fifteen-year-old students in the Philippines performed worse in reading than students in the majority of the participating nations and economies in the 2018 PISA exam. At 340 points, the nation's average reading score was comparable to that of the Dominican Republic. Out of all the countries, the Philippines and the Dominican Republic scored the lowest. Additionally assessed is the students' capacity for innovation; in 2018, this area was global competence.

Considerably, there was no significant difference between the experimental and control groups' means in a study on the effect of TBI on improving ninth-graders' English-speaking skills. Before the experiment, both groups of students had the same level of English proficiency. Both groups' means increased considerably in the posttests. The experimental group's mean, on the other hand, was much higher, indicating a better level of speaking ability (Nget, 2020). The outcomes were carefully considered, both behavioral and quantifiable, and the instructions were provided in an easy-to-understand manner. Furthermore, instructors' language skills may have an effect on students' learning (Nemati et al., 2017). As supported by this study, the experimental group performed satisfactorily while the control group performed fairly satisfactorily. Hence, the students under the experimental group had better learning progress than the control group. The level of validity of the Task-Based Approach Learning was highly valid. The TBA module was of great help in increasing student achievement.

Moreover, students in the experimental group performed better than the students in the control group. The application of the Task-Based Approach module is effective as to the content and relevance of task-based activities through the task cycle in the new normal, which contributed to the increase in performance scores of the respondents. Finally, teachers should also be able to design language activities that will cater to EFL learners' needs, attitudes, and behavior to become successful in language learning (Ulla, 2017).

K to 12 Curriculum and Task-Based Language Approaches

TBLT is one of the approaches to language learning which suggests learning by doing (Moore, 2018). When all respondents (100%) agreed and intended to study materials in sequence, ranging from the easiest to the most complicated, the data supported this. Similarly, when it came to real-life learning activities, 100% of respondents agreed and requested material that was relevant to their everyday lives and academics in junior high (Anwar & Arifani, 2016). In addition, the writing skills of Iranian EFL students who utilized task-based strategies improved significantly compared to those who used standard writing activities (Kafipour et al., 2018). According to the Teaching Approaches of Subjects in K to 12, while establishing the improved basic education curriculum, the DepEd must follow the following criteria and principles: a. Learner-centered, inclusive, and developmentally appropriate curriculum is required.

Furthermore, the curriculum must foster competency in both Filipino and English, with the primary language of instruction being the learners' first and dominant language. Instruction, teaching materials, and assessment in Kindergarten and the first three years of primary school must be in the learners' regional or native language. (K to 12 Curriculum Section 5 of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013).

Because of this, K-12 reform ought to go beyond simply altering the structure of the country's educational system; rather, it ought to revolutionize the educational process, pushing all parties involved to reconsider how they teach and learn and to adopt more demanding, pertinent, and experience-based learning models (Savi et al., 2015).

Related studies of Task-based Approach versus other approaches

In a study on the use of task-based methods to language education, preliminary findings of statistical analysis suggested that task-based language teaching resulted in higher fluency and complexity. The task-based method, it was believed, produces a more suitable environment for learning a second language. As a result, it can be argued that task-based language education enables better learning and improves learners' oral skills performance.

For task-based versus task-supported language learning, Li et al. (2016) discovered that explicit teaching combined with within-task feedback was more effective than the other treatment groups. Another study found that forty students improved significantly in all four areas. TBL was beneficial because the students used more English, learnt, and comprehended outside of class when they completed homework, had more practice, understood more, and learned how to collaborate with others, according to the open-ended question. They also suggested that TBL be utilized in conjunction with other courses due to its numerous learning benefits (Chorthip, 2018).

Furthermore, the learners have no linguistic control, unlike in a PPP method. Rather of rehearsing one pre-selected thing, they must utilize all of their linguistic resources in all three levels. TBA is a communication strategy where students talk for extended periods of time. PPP classes seem to be more traditional in contrast.

Strengths of TBL Approach

Learners can utilize whatever linguistic skills they know in task-based learning to interact spontaneously. A role-play, for example, requires the learner to freely utilize words. It allows students to practice any language they already know. It also allows students to notice and profit from the expressions of others, gradually increasing their confidence. As they complete a task, the learners' cognitive and communication abilities improve. This outcome is consistent with the study for the sub-theme of why students love learning,

Aqmar et al. (2020) revealed that majority of the respondents gained knowledge English through task-based activities in speaking courses.

Because TBLT is more successful at completing writing tasks in the classroom than traditional writing activities, Iranian EFL students who used task-based methods improved much more than those who used traditional writing activities (Kafipour, R., 2018). In addition, Mulyadi et al. (2021) also looked into the effects of technology assisted TBLT on learners' listening comprehension and speaking abilities. The experimental group's listening scores outperformed the control group, according to the test results. As an outcome, the use of technology to improve TBLT had a favorable impact on the learners' listening comprehension. Teng (2015) similarly found that, while both groups increased their word knowledge, the experimental group outperformed the control group in terms of mastery.

Hence, teachers should think of new methods to immerse students in the pre-task since words taught in this manner are readily forgotten. It also creates necessary settings for language learning: stimulus, experience, and opportunity to use the language are all necessary for language learning.

Teachers' Role in Task-based Approach

In order to properly prepare students for completing tasks, teachers must take an active role in pre-teaching lexicogrammatical structures and motivating their peers. For any strategy to be successful, teachers must be incredibly creative and inventive in engaging students and taking steps to capture their interest. When an instructor is talented, learning opportunities are increased. Consequently, the instructor ought to seize every opportunity to enhance the pupils' performance and equip them to apply language in authentic situations in future endeavors (Ganta, 2015).

Furthermore, the findings are similar with Anwar and Arifani's (2016) study, in which all respondents (100%) agreed and intended to learn materials in sequence, starting with the easiest and progressing to the most difficult.

Furthermore, the teacher should keep an eye on how the learners deal with their challenges and withstand any pressure to provide answers. The teacher's responsibility is to provide pointers and, if required, make the work simpler. On the other hand, the teacher observes the students at work with two separate evaluation viewpoints in mind: the acquisition of knowledge and work accomplishments. Students at work provide firsthand raw material for identifying the students' learning requirements. While the students are engaged in their work, the teacher begins to prepare future EDC/HRE lecture sequences. The teacher can also volunteer to be "called upon" as a source of information on demand, briefing a group on a pressing subject.

Teaching and learning in the new normal

Approximately 75% of students worldwide have been affected by school closures brought on by the COVID-19 epidemic (UNESCO, 2020). 91.3 percent of all students enrolled in 188 nations are enrolled there, with roughly 1,576,021,818 students (Toquero, 2020). Even so, just 25.4% of the 27.7 million students enrolled in elementary and secondary education remain, accounting for 74.6 percent of the total. Among the most important concerns of this virtual opening of courses are access to the appropriate technology required for distance learning, educational initiatives and instructional materials, and online program for a modular style (Altbach & De Wit, 2020; HESB, 2020).

According to the Department of Education, the pandemic has adapted and make lives and experiences in ways that no one could have predicted. The unique circumstance presented difficulties and possibilities to many community and societal sectors. Because face-to-face encounters and social events are limited, the Department of Education, with its primary purpose of providing accessible and high-quality education to Filipino students, insists that learning must continue regardless the epidemic. As a result, blended learning is used to execute remote learning.

Modular and online distance learning, learning management systems, and television/radio-based education are the three types of remote learning. With modular distance learning, students can employ self-learning modules (SLMs) in paper or digital format.

Noting that classroom assessment is a crucial aspect of executing the curriculum, according to DepEd Order No. 8 (2015). It becomes the foundation for evaluating pupils' performance and growth. It also serves as a criterion for making essential changes to the instructional methodologies as outlined in the policy guidelines. As a result, instructors' roles should be more inventive, motivating students to actively participate in virtually and engaging students beyond their limits to achieve the intended educational outcomes (Tuscano, 2020).

Because TBLT is already commonly used in Foreign Language situations, the findings support the assumption that it has good impacts on Second Language Acquisition. Most study findings in Asian nations imply that implementation is challenging. Several research have focused on the difficulties that TBLT brings when employed in FL settings (Isabel & Farfan, 2019).

On the contrary, the ESL teaching setting did not ensure that all students would grasp the lesson because of their English competence. Furthermore, according to Permatasari (2021), the genuine output is appreciated when it is in the form of an English language paper that combines real-life situations that students have faced in the TBLT Method in Google Classroom Application for English Learning Approach.

Methodology

Respondents

The following are the inclusion criteria of the respondents of the study. The study respondents were the selected G-10 students of San Emmanuel National High School (SENHS) enrolled for 2020-2021. There were two sets of respondents of this study, (1) those 20 from G-10 Magsaysay who used the teacher-made task-based approach module in LMS and those 20 from G-10 Laurel who used the DepEd module in Modular Distance Learning. Additionally, there were (5) validators who validated this study having an inclusion criteria.

Instruments

The instrument for the independent variable was adapted from the Measuring green marketing: scale development and validation questionnaire (Vilkaite-vaitone et al., 2022). The green marketing contained a total of 15 items. Strategy (3 items), Internal Marketing (3 items), Product (3 items), and Marketing Communication (3 items).

Furthermore, this questionnaire was anchored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 5- Strongly Agree, 4- Agree, 3- Moderately Agree, 2- Disagree, and 1- Strongly Disagree. The following parameter limits, with their corresponding descriptions, were applied to the level of green marketing.

The instrument used in this study was a teacher-made task-based module downloaded into LMS, which covered different topics with competencies relevant to the subject. It covered pre-task activities, actual tasks, post-task review activities, and homework/assignment or practice. In addition, the validation tool used in the evaluation of the module was adapted from DepEd's Learning Resource Management Development (LRMDS). It was validated based on the following criteria: content, relevance, instructional quality, and acceptability with the rating and descriptor of 5 being excellent, 4 as very satisfactory, 3 as satisfactory, 2 as poor and 1 as not satisfactory. The test items for the pretest and posttest were adapted from the DepEd G-10 English Learning material.

The selected 30 students of San Emmanuel National High School under the K to 12 curriculum were used to test the research instrument's reliability. Grade 11 were not the study's respondents, and they had already taken the lessons and passed the lessons involved in this study.

The consolidated results were tabulated and computed using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 to determine the reliability coefficient of the (40) item test. The computed correlation coefficient of the instrument was 0.91 which denotes a very high correlation. Thus, the instrument of this study was reliable.

To determine the level of academic achievement of the respondents, the score had transformed to a percentage score then transmuted using the DepEd Order No. 8 s. 2015 with the corresponding grading scale as shown on table 1. The TBA Module which was employed by the researcher was evaluated by the respondents who undergone the TBA and content validators.

Table 1. *Descriptions, Grading Scale, and Remarks*

Descriptors	Grading Scale	Remarks
Outstanding	90-100	Passed
Very Satisfactory	85-89	Passed
Satisfactory	80-84	Passed
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	Passed
Did not meet expectations	74 and below	Failed

Validity of the Tasked-Based Approach Module (TBA-Module)

The level of validity of this module was validated through the following criteria: content, relevance, instructional quality, and acceptability.

In Table 2, the level of validity of the Task-Based Approach Learning is highly valid, with an overall mean of 4.72. It can be inferred that the TBA learning module was of great help in attaining the increase of student's achievement, as shown in the data. It indicates that the module meets the criteria in content, relevance, instructional quality, and acceptability, implying that it is suitable for use in the TBLT. On the contrary, a study by Alavi et al. (2018) on the Validity of the Listening Module of the International English Language Testing System discovered that a highly valid test in one context might be invalid in another one. Furthermore, using self-instruction methods like pamphlets and instructional modules, which are an approach to education, could be a better option because the individual can determine the time and place of learning.

Table 2. *Summary of the Validity of Task-Based Approach Module*

Dimension	Mean Rating	Interpretation
Content	4.71	Highly Valid
Relevance	4.72	Highly Valid
Instructional Quality	4.77	Highly Valid
Acceptability	4.70	Highly Valid
Overall Mean	4.72	Highly Valid

Results and Discussion

Students' Level of Academic Achievement

The researcher calculated the mean scores for the experimental and control groups, converted them to percentage scores, and then used the DepEd Order No. 8, Series 2015 transmutation table, which is also known as the Policy and Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K–12 Basic Education Program, to determine the students' level of academic achievement. The same DepEd Order descriptors were used to report the transmuted scores from the pretest and posttest.

Table 3. *Level of Students' Achievement in Pretest*

Group	SD	Mean Score	Equivalent	Description
Control	5.70	21.30	70%	Did Not Meet Expectation
Experimental	4.83	20.15	70%	Did Not Meet Expectation

Table 3 shows the level of academic achievement of CG and EG in the pretest. Both groups had a mean score of 21.30 and 20.15, respectively. The results reveal that both groups did not meet the expectations in their achievement, which means that both groups had the same level of learning progress before the start of the experiment. This result is supported by Teng (2015) where both groups improved in terms of word knowledge, the experimental group attained better outcomes about mastery. It also revealed that both groups' best-learned word knowledge was form recognition, followed by meaning recognition, meaning, and form recall. It also aligns with Wang et al.'s (2021) study on Facilitating English Grammar Learning by a Personalized Mobile-Assisted System with Self-Regulated Learning. Both groups had similar pretest scores. A significant interaction between time and condition in the English grammar test scores. However, TBLT implementation may vary due to cultural differences (Isabel & Farfan, 2019).

Table 4. *Level of Students' Achievement in Posttest*

Group	SD	Mean Score	Equivalent	Description
Control	1.75	32.00	77%	Fairly Satisfactory
Experimental	3.21	36.70	83%	Satisfactory

Table 4 reveals that the experimental group performed better than the control group. The EG obtained a satisfactory level, as evidenced by a mean of 36.70. In contrast, the CG has a fairly satisfactory level with a mean of 32.00. It means that the students under the EG had better learning progress than the CG. This outcome is consistent with the findings of Aqmar et al. (2020), who found that implementing the task-based module in a speaking lesson improves students' achievement. The respondents stated that task-based learning and activities were enjoyable ways to learn English.

Furthermore, the result is consistent with Anwar and Arifani (2016) study, when all respondents (100%) agreed and desired to learn resources in sequential order, ranging from the easiest to the most complex. Similarly, when it came to real-life learning activities, all respondents (100%) agreed and desired information relevant to their daily lives and studies in junior high. This study shows that employing a task-based learning module is adequate to boost students' speaking skills, owing to task-based activities. Students find it easier to enunciate words or phrases and communicate the basic idea of the topics they have learned and discussed (Aqmar et al., 2020).

Difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups

Table 5. *The t-test analysis on the Pretest Score of the Control Group and Experimental Group*

Groups	n	Mean	t _{computed value}	Tabulated t-value	Interpretation
Control Group	20	21.30	0.68	2.09	Not Significant
Experimental Group	20	20.15			

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 5 reveals that the t-computed value is 0.68 and is lesser than the t-critical value of 2.09 at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted that there was no significant difference between the pretest scores of the EG and CG. This means that the groups had almost the same level of achievement during the pretest. Hence, the EG and CG students had the same understanding of the topics incorporated in the pretest exam. Meanwhile, Table 9 reveals the students' level of achievement in the pretest. It is also supported by the Nget (2020) study, which concluded that there is no significant difference between the means of the EG and CG. In the posttests, the means of both groups increased significantly. However, the experimental group's mean was significantly greater than that of the control group at the 0.05 level, indicating a higher speaking skills level.

The result is consistent with Li et al.'s (2016) experimental study on Task-Based Versus Task-Supported Language Instruction, which indicated that explicit instruction combined with within-task feedback was more effective than the other treatment types. Additionally, Kafipour (2018) mentioned how task-based language instruction affects analytical writing in EFL classes. Both groups did poorly on the writing pretest, as evidenced by the mean score of 8.17 (out of 20) that two raters assigned to the control group's performance on the writing pretest and the mean score of 8.10 (out of 20) that the same raters assigned to the experimental group's performance on the writing posttest, with standard deviations of 1.19 and 1.17, respectively.

The Difference among the Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 6. *The t-test Analysis on the Posttest score of the Control Group and Experimental Group*

Groups	n	Mean	t _{computed value}	Tabulated t-value	Interpretation
Control Group	20	32.00	5.91	2.09	Significant
Experimental Group	20	36.70			

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 6 unveils that the t-computed value of 5.91 is greater than the t-critical value of 2.09 at a .05 level of significance. It means that the null hypothesis is rejected that there is no significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental group. It is noticeable that the mean of EG is higher than the CG of 36.70 and 32.00, respectively. It implies that students in the experimental group had greater learning progress using the Task-based Learning module with the integration of the learning management system than students who use Self-learning modules.

This finding is consistent with the findings of Aqmar et al. (2020), who found that most respondents enjoyed learning English through task-based activities in speaking lessons. Gao and Li (2017) found out also that the EG had more improvement in reading comprehension than the CG using the task-based reading model. Moreover, Ulla (2017) reveals that students were more positive about doing different tasks in their language classrooms than not. In addition, the writing skills of Iranian EFL students who utilized task-based strategies improved significantly compared to those who used standard writing activities. Conversely, from a culturally and critically informed standpoint, TBLT has only engaged with a portion of the activities that it has selected. Integrating a more critical viewpoint into task design and content, as well as curriculum creation, may be beneficial. Furthermore, the use of task-based writing strategies greatly increased learners' skills in several facets of writing competency, particularly sentence structure, language use, grammar, content, and order (Kafipour et al., 2018).

The Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control Group and Experimental Group

Table 7 reveals that the students in the CG have a significant difference in their scores from pretest to posttest, with a mean of 21.30 and 32.00, respectively. The t-computed value of 8.09 is greater than the t-critical value of 2.09 at a .05 level of significance. It means that their scores had a significant increase in the posttest. It implies that using the Self-learning module provided by DepEd Region XII positively affected the students' learning achievement.

Table 7. *The t-test Analysis on Pretest and Posttest score of the Control Group and Experimental Group*

Groups	Mean	t _{computed value}	Tabulated t-value	Interpretation
Control Group				
Pretest	21.30	8.09	2.09	Significant
Posttest	32.00			
Mean Score Difference	10.7			
Experimental Group				
Pretest	20.15	14.27	2.09	Significant
Posttest	36.7			
Mean Score Difference	16.55			

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

On the one hand, students under the EG also had a significant difference in their pretest to posttest scores, with a mean of 20.15 and 36.7, respectively. The t-computed value of 14.27 is greater than the t-critical value of 2.09 at a 0.05 level of significance.

On the other hand, the students increased their scores during the posttest compared to their pretest scores. It implies that the researcher made the Task-based Approach learning module has a good effect on the academic achievement of the respondents.

On the contrary, the ESL teaching context did not guarantee that all students have good English proficiency in understanding the instruction. (Hapsari, 2020.) Furthermore, despite the positive motivation of the students to improve their speaking skills, and despite the number of students who had a high level of motivation to use English in the classroom, there were still several who found it challenging to use English in speaking when talking to their classmates (51%) and their teacher (42%). It is evident that many of them only had an average level of motivation in using the English language (Ulla, 2017). Furthermore, according to Permatasari (2021), in The Task-Based Language Teaching Method in the Google Classroom Application for English Learning Approach, the real product is valued when it is in the shape of an English language paper that incorporates real-life issues that students have encountered. Moreover, the linguistic ability of teachers may also influence student learning (Nemati et al., 2017).

The Difference between the Mean Gain Scores of the Control and the Experimental Groups

Table 8. *The t-test analysis on the difference of the Mean Gain scores of Control Group and Experimental Group*

Groups	Mean Gain	SD	Main Gain Difference	t _{computed value}	Tabulated t-value	Interpretation
Control Group	10.70	5.91	5.85	3.09	2.09	Significant
Experimental Group	16.55	5.19				

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 8 shows the difference in the mean gain scores of the students exposed to SLM (control group) compared to those who utilized the Task-based Approach learning module (EG). The EG had a mean gain score of 16.55, which is greater than the mean gain score of the CG, which is 10.70. The comparison is decided by a t-computed value of 3.09, greater than the critical value of 2.09 at a 0.05 level of significance.

It means that there is a significant difference in the mean gain scores of the control and experimental group. Students under the EG performed better compared to the student in the CG. It implies that the application of the Task-Based Approach learning module is effective as to the content and relevance of task-based activities through the task cycle in the new normal, which contributed to the increase in performance scores of the respondents. Alternatively, a study shows that standardized evaluations and large classes are the biggest challenges teachers report when implementing TBLT (Isabel & Farfan, 2019).

In other notion, tasks have to be negotiated by the learners with the teacher's help, whose job is to facilitate learning opportunities in

class. In Asian countries, most of the research results indicate that it is difficult to implement. In several studies, authors have focused on the challenges that TBLT presents when implemented in FL contexts (Isabel & Farfan, 2019). Moreover, rather than accepting accountability for their acts, students would rather be instructed what to do, particularly in Asian societies where academics are still seen as "sage on the stage." In addition, TBLT in online learning, for example, in Google Classroom, greatly impacted speaking ability. Both students and teachers gained new experiences due to the English learning approach. It gives students and teachers certain advantages in performing teaching and learning processes (Permatasari, 2021).

The study determined the effectiveness of applying a researcher-made TBA-Module in Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) under new normal utilizing the LMS to improve students' academic achievement in English 10 of San Emmanuel National High School at San Emmanuel, Tacurong City.

This study utilized a Quasi-Experimental, pretest-posttest control group design. A treatment group was given a pretest, received a treatment, and then a posttest. The experimental group used the Task-based approach module in LMS. In contrast, the control group was exposed to the DepEd self-learning module.

The TBA-Module obtained a highly valid level of validity about its content, relevance, instructional quality, and acceptability, as supported by the overall mean of 4.72.

In the pretest, EG and CG obtained mean scores of 21.30 and 20.15, respectively. Both groups did not meet their achievement expectations, and they showed the same level of learning progress before experimentation. On the other hand, the EG performed better in the posttest than the CG. The EG reached a mean of 36.70 (Satisfactory Level). At the same time, the CG had a mean of 32.00 (Fairly Satisfactory Level).

Based on the findings of the study, the following hypotheses were accepted and rejected:

First, the null hypothesis was accepted as to the significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental group. It means that the groups had almost the same level of achievement during the pretest. Thus, the EG and CG students had the same understanding of the topics incorporated in the pretest exam. Second, the null hypothesis was rejected as to the significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental group. The students in the experimental group had greater learning progress using the Task-based Learning module with the integration of the learning management system than students who used Self-learning modules. The third is that the null hypothesis is accepted as to the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control and experimental groups. Their scores had a significant increase in the posttest. Using the Self-learning module provided by DepEd Region XII positively affected the students' learning achievement.

Finally, the null hypothesis is rejected as to the significant difference between the mean gain scores of the control and experimental groups. It means that there is a significant difference in the mean gain scores of the control and experimental group. Students under the EG performed better compared to the student in the CG. The application of the Task-Based Approach learning module is effective as to the content and relevance of task-based activities through the task cycle in the new normal, which contributed to the increase in performance scores of the respondents.

The students in the control group had significant differences in their scores from pretest to posttest, with a mean of 21.30 and 32.00, respectively, resulting in the t-computed value of 8.09, which is greater than the t-critical value of 2.09 at a .05 level of significance. It implies that using the Self-learning module provided by DepEd Region XII positively affected the students' learning achievement.

Students in the experimental group, on the other hand, had a significant difference in their scores from pretest to posttest, with mean scores of 20.15 and 36.7, respectively, resulting in a t-computed value of 14.27, which is greater than the t-critical value of 2.09 at the 0.05 level of significance. It signifies that the respondents' posttest scores improved compared to their pretest scores. The Task-based Approach learning module created by the researcher positively impacted the respondents' academic achievement.

The difference in the mean gain scores of the students exposed to SLM (control group) compared to the students' utilized Task-based Approach learning module (experimental group). The experimental group had a mean gain of 16.55, greater than the mean gain of the control group of 10.70. The comparison is decided by the t-computed value of 3.09, greater than the critical value of 2.09 at a 0.05 level of significance. There was a significant difference in the mean gain scores of the control and experimental group. Students in the experimental group performed better than those in the control group, which means that the Task-Based Approach learning module is effective in terms of the substance and relevance of task-based activities throughout the task cycle under new normal, contributing to the respondents' improved performance scores.

Conclusion

The researcher therefore concluded that the Task-based Approach module is effective in teaching language under new normal. This is based on the revealed results of the study. The teacher-made task-based approach module was rated high valid in terms of content, relevance, instructional qualities and acceptability, with this result, it is found relative because the study shows an evident progress to the students after the TBA module was used, hence using the TBA, a self-learning module provide positive effect to the students learning achievement.

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